

УДК

**GRAMMATICAL REDUCTION AND SIMPLIFICATION IN THE ENGLISH-
LANGUAGE OF «INSTAGRAM»**

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Annotation: *The aim of this article lies on linguistic transformation of English within the digital space, based on the materials of Instagram social media discourse. Especially paying attention to grammatical reduction and simplification linguistic phenomena, which appears in syntactic constructions, left out auxiliary verbs, frequent use of incomplete and nonstandard sentences and their grammatical forms. These processes are seen not just as language degradation sign but as adaptive mechanism providing speed, expressiveness and informality of the communication as well in the conditions of visual orientated online discourse platform Instagram.*

Keywords: *Social media, Instagram, linguistic features, digital communication, reduction and simplification*

Digital communication makes language dynamic, flexible, adaptive. The aim of this article lies on demonstrating a new linguistic tendency such as grammar reduction and simplification faced on well-known social media Instagram. High relevance of the article is confirmed through the real observation reflected on users` interaction on this social media. Today each of us follows their favorite digital figures for some reasons. However, is there the influence of their posts to our own speech? There are endless bloggers and representatives of any sphere and they express their minds appropriate to their field of activity they do. People now prefer online interaction the most, so that`s why there are many platforms showing up every time. Instagram one the most popular and frequently used social media which allows everybody post visual illustrations with caption where they can share their thoughts, ask for some ideas, comment each other and interact with the audience. It is seen how users simplify the speech there. Sometimes this comes in handy concerning expression some kind of emotions. Although, new English learners face difficulties because of this and the reasons for that may be the fact they are supposed to learn the language in traditional way.

This article was written on the base of several methods and approaches to explore the theme through the different prism of views. First of all, in order to reveal the influence of digitalization development on words` historical transformation historical and etymological approach was used. Descriptive and analytical method covered the idea of grammatical adaptation of the language in digital discourse communication conditions. Functional approach responses for people`s frequent usage of simplification and answers what could cause the continuation of this linguistic phenomena and the connection between function of the statements and chosen definite grammatical structure is explained. The differences between traditional and digital adapted speech using constant reduction and simplification are seen through comparative method.

Literature review

Blogosphere took its root in 1992. The word blog that we hear every day was created in 1997 by J.Barger, although originally sounded as *weblog*. Then after two years, it was shorten to blog by P.Merholz and P.Labs Company borrowed this expression making it requested in many web services and even became a word of the year by Merriam-Webster`s Dictionary in 2014. If the word blog is

suitable for written texts, then *vlogs* which is formed by adding «blog» and «video» let people speak up their thoughts in video materials being considered as a part of blogosphere as well [1].

N. Baron says that the word *Blog* originally comes from *web log* which was created by J. Barger in 1997 [2]. Firstly, it meant a list of website URLs. Nowadays this term is used by those who broadcast their lives or any other activities shooting on camera and share their content on digital discourses. She divides users' interaction management into 3 parts. In her book, she mentions increasing the opportunities of actual talking to definite people as the first type. Second is recommendation to avoid mechanisms in order to avert linguistic encounters while manipulation relays on the third one. In the context of social media these strategies mentioned above shows how language reflects the person's identity, self-presentation on their accounts. Nevertheless, English we see on online discourses truly challenge traditional language we are used to.

As R. Page [3] describes in her work *Narrative Online Stories* dominate our contemporary communicative landscape. People post short Instagram stories to interact with their followers or share some new from their lives. It even can be important in promotion a particular way of representing events, people and places. R. Page revealed three aspects of the mediated discourse. First of all she mentioned the ways that stories serve as mediators for their tellers. Secondly, how they are shaped or influenced by their digital environments. Eventually, R. Page accents on the positions that are mediated between the tellers and their social contexts). The researcher shared that narrative needs to be clear and certain. When there is no even greeting the sentence wouldn't be appropriate with the forms of narrative. So the importance of clear reports is required describing any events.

Several researchers tried to explain this tendency which is definitely prominent on Instagram and why it is pretty frequent among modern content makers. Grammatical simplification and syntactic reduction are the most notable features belong to those who want their speech look more natural and unusual at the same time. D. Crystal who spoke on *Netspeak* noted that it lacks facial expressions, gestures in the real-time communication. Instead, people just use smileys to express their feelings, replace the text by emojis making their speech simple which is not always shows the truth and can regulate their roles after which writing may be trapped into ambiguity, meanings can be changed while omissions and readers do not catch the idea of the released posts [4].

Frequent use of reduction and simplification in speech can serve as the result of worldwide distribution of English, which is taught in a plenty of countries as a second/foreign language all over the world. As L. Pavlyukevich declares [5], the cause of this tendency may come from the representatives of other cultures except British and those who speak English at low levels often affect the language functions a lot. Reduction and simplification are reflected in all their aspects of speech activity. However even the native speakers barely try to use Future Perfect and mostly switch on Future Simple tense and often refuse to use *shall* and prefer *will* everywhere which leads to grammatical simplification.

Since there are thousands of English learners, simplification is believed to provide comfortable conditions between native and non-native speakers during the interactions according to I. Zhorova [6]. The researcher says that all language system and its subsystem are simplified so British and other cultures' people demonstrate linguistic simplifications of one's language showing that it is crucial for language's dynamic development and qualitative changes for the modern life.

Having read *Digital Discourse: Language in the New Media* book, we can see the scheme coding of text-to-screen replication. C. Thurlow, K. Mroczek tried to illustrate it through the table [7]. They wrote that punctuation, spelling, word replacement differ from original. They mentioned a few of acronyms which one of them is LOL that means laugh out loud and can be replaced by «Hahaha». This may demonstrate a sarcasm too. There are reduplications such as «k», «u», «mntg», «btw» «ain`»t «brugh» which are for «okey», «you», «meeting», «by the way», «isn't», «bro». In one of his examples [7] there is a text full of capitalization: «LOLOLOLOLOL! That's BECAUSE IT MAKES NO SENSE, I WILL FIGURE OUT WHEN AND HOW WE CAN SPEND THE REST OF OUR LIVES TOGETHER!». It's obviously seen that the author is extremely excited about his thought and expresses it through so-called scream, which is understandable for readers. They even could read out

the text with the right intonation as well. As C.Thurlow, K.Mroczek noted, written text's modification should be followed by standard. Most of the messages have some alteration.

Bloggers usually take advantages of standardization and move some remove nonstandard features in English. From the book's example [7], there is an example «*Renee is going to be fired off of EPU! Found out she been talking to IA about things going on over here*». This sentence would include *has* in *she been* and *It is* before *Found out* to make the sentence grammatically correct. Even though, the first sentence doesn't have omission of *Be going* to grammatical construction.

A.Moghees, S.Abbas, D.Mehr, Z.M.Saeed [8] together made a table comparing CMC and Standard Grammar Forms in their works. Just kidding, Just chatting, going fr wrk (which is for I am going for work), lukin difrtn (looking different), feelin so much wcknes (I am feeling so much weakness), hey looking cute (hey, you are looking cute), when coming back? (when are you coming back?), and other lot of examples from the table are the reflection of linguistic modern changes. They checked 300 messages and in 40 out of them, it was noted that there were omissions of pronouns and auxiliaries. People often skip pronouns in the beginning of the sentence and *to be* (am, is, are) in continuous tenses. In that case, these changes are rapidly spreading in internet speech.

Ellipsis, omissions, simplifications, reduplication are encouraged in everyday life and this is common for written forms of speech as well. According to Cambridge Dictionary, reduction is the act of making something, or of something becoming, smaller in size, amount, degree, importance. Simplification and reduction serve functional and social purposes. One of the reason for use of them can be a speed. Now people always are in a rush and making writing, affecting on spelling let them write faster than it could be skipping the formality. Influencers may deliberately use colloquial or reduced grammar to appear relatable and "real" to their audience. We know that these simplifications are used not without purpose. All the abbreviations, reduplications have their own transcripts. Gretchen McCulloch [9] explains that using all capitals of a word means shouting, screaming to express extremely loud emotions and the usage of 3-dot ellipsis means someone makes a pause or sometimes thoughts might be continued. It is also possible that writer thinks that the audience understand mind of his/her so even the ellipsis can talk about a lot than the full-text. Sometimes people reveal passive-aggressive feelings towards the certain topic or even figures through it.

Many researchers discussed that digital communication leads to linguistic simplification during digital communication. Especially noticeable the repetition of *u* for *you* under post captions of Instagram users. Social media encourage brevity at the expense of correctness.

Now it's been challengeable for learners to differ formal and informal speech which says that social media blur the borders boundaries between colloquial and academic writing. People are used to speak informally so they even think informally and usually that's why they may face some difficulties when switching into academic language.

However, this is not an issue. Some researchers recommend consider linguistic register, which consists of formal, informal and neutral depended on the theme and target. Experts of concerned sphere should be involved in consulting the specialized reduction. One of the aspect that should be noted is that abbreviation needs to be readable in the context of comprehension. Readers mustn't feel anxiety to figure out the relevance of them. Translations of abbreviation's have to be grammatically accurate and it doesn't to go out of its context. L.S.Ismayilova tell us that speech need to save its professionalism [10].

There are numbers of abbreviations noticed from Instagram posts. For example:

Abbreviation	Transcript
ASMR	Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response
DM	Direct Message
BTS	Behind the scenes
BTW	By the way
GRWM	Get ready with me
HBD	Happy birthday

IG	Instagram
ILY/IMU	I love you/ I miss you
LMK	Let me know
OMG	Oh my God
Thx	Thanks

Table 1. Common abbreviations and their transcripts (created by the author, data collected from social media resources)

Here are the real examples from Instagram users. Instagram page @asmreatingtube uses «ASMR and DM for collabs» in her profile bio.

Korean user @ssuu_als posted pictures using HBD

There are over 9.1 million posts used hashtag *GRWM*. Now it's one of the most trendy abbreviation applied on Instagram. Abbreviation *OMG* is used under 23.6 million posts nowadays.

Asian users prefer to reduce *Thank you* to *Thx*. There are a lot of posts from China, Thailand, Japan where they express their gratitude through *thx*.

@haeriury dedicated a post for her friend saying «Used to stick together you're my bsf ily forever». There are even two more abbreviations which are *bsf* that is best friend and *ily* which stands for I love you and the simplification of *you're* instead of you are.

Another way of simplifying digital speech is the simplification of syntax. I.Ahmad, M.Shaffaqat, A.Azam tried to research this direction and noted this is one of the key linguistic features which simplifies both spoken and written language. People often replace complex sentences by simple, reduce passive voice application, omit pronoun, connection of sentences without subordination. Omission of punctuation, capital letters are common among teenagers and young adults. Researchers' position is that this takes place not because of the laziness of people, but a conscious choice to manage the speech style. Moreover, there are new ways to reduce long formal texts with voice messages, GIFs and video reactions. Such syntax reduction cause the way of thinking and information acceptance [11].

This article identified common linguistic features such as reduction and grammar simplification faced on one of the digital discourses Instagram, which has millions of users. This phenomenon shows that English is still evolving in response to technological and social changes. The tendency of users to simplify the structures of words, phrases, sentences, texts reducing auxiliary verbs, skipping article and punctuation, using frequent abbreviations covers their emotional need that used to lack in past. Now everyone adopted to such kind of speech during online interactions. These simplifications could be considered as indicators of language innovation and flexibility because people often manipulate language to make their speech unique, individual. Moreover, the observation on grammatical reduction and simplification shows the growing tendency nowadays on social media language and it is not just an ordinary cases. Real Instagram based examples highlight practical significance of the research and confirm its high relevance in conditions of continuing language norms. So, this article demonstrates the deep understanding the fact that digital reality forms new models of language behavior.

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